

PRAGMATIC REFERENCE IN LITERARY DISCOURSE

Qosimova Nafisa Farxodovna

PhD, Docent, Bukhara State University

Haydarova Gulnora Rajabovna

Bukhara State University first year master's student

Abstract: *This article is devoted to discourse analyses which discusses the reference and its main types. Particularly, this study aims at showing the importance of raising learners' awareness as to the use of cataphoric references in discourse. In addition, it studies the reference and its types comparatively and finds out similarities and dissimilarities of the reference in the Uzbek and English languages. And, in accordance with what has shortly explained above, this paper will also try to answer these questions: [1] what is the definition of reference? [2] What are features of it and some examples of reference in literary discourse?*

Keywords: *Reference, cataphora, anaphora, referent, coherence, cohesion, exophora, endophora, discourse, semantics, anaphora, cataphora, analysis, expressive, argument, poetic, narrative.*

The meaning and value of a literary text, as well as the meaning and value of the sentence, is created by means of formal elements of the language, such as morphology, syntax and semantics. However, the meaning of the same literary text in relation to the communicative context, as well as the meaning of the statement, is created by pragmatics – the attitude of words to the one from whom they proceed and to the one who these statements or words are addressed to. And this is a secondary understanding of the text meaning in the communicative context and appears as a pragmatic basis for interpreting the literary text. Another approach to studying the issue includes a pragmatic structure and interpretation strategies. (Kasimova N. F., 2021)

Communication is essential for everyone to express feelings, exchange information, delivering messages and many other functions of it. During the act of communication human use language, containing sentences, words and smaller units which also contribute to construct meaning. One distinctive character of human language is the act of describing about something outside which has been known as 'aboutness' phenomenon (Hockett & Attman, 1968). Human don't only talk about something visible around them, but also abstract concept. Since the things which

human talk about is outside, they need to describe them using words, phrases or sentences. Thus, the concept of ‘reference’ is proclaimed and become interesting issue to be explored by linguists.

Reference is defined as a thing that speaker says or writes that mentions something or somebody else (Oxford Advanced Learner Dictionary, 8th Edition). Yule (1997) defined it as an action in which communicator utilizes a linguistic forms in order to direct listeners into identification of something. Sullivan (in Allan & Jaszczolt, 2012) described it as the relation that obtains between as use of linguistic expression and what it stands for or denotes. Russel (in Allan & Jaszczolt, 2012) differentiated between reference and denotation. As reference is specific and mainstream link between an expression, referent or role; referring is simply labelling or tagging something. Meanwhile -according to him- denotation is a unique link between expression and something, with a satisfying specific condition and semantically well-expressed. Strawson (1950) challenged this theory by emphasizing that referring is not done by the expression, but it is a thing that can be utilized by human to do.

If reference is done by and depends on speakers’ goal, inference is listeners’ task to discover the relationship between expressed entities with the words (Yule, 1997). It is also defined as ‘making assertion’ using what listener or reader catch from speakers’ or writers’ linguistic expression, and accepted as truth even it was clearly stated (Norvig, 2007). It is clearly a cognitive process happening inside the human (listener/reader) mind, transforming available and explicit information to create understanding (Wills, 2017).

During the communication, complex sentences are used to provide enough elaboration as needed by the speaker. And it is almost impossible to always use short expression separately. Thus, references are sometimes repeated again and again. But it would be peculiar to always use complete reference again and again. Hence, anaphoric reference takes its role to link back the reference. Take a look on the example below:

It is stated in the book that *Pete and Joanna* got married at the end of 2019. Shortly after that, *they* stayed in a small house in the peaceful village, far away from people who always disturb *them*. Two years later, *they* had a beautiful and cute baby boy, named Alex. *They* named him Alex as they wish that *he* will be a great-man in the future, contributing for the religion and country life.

[Pete and Joanna] is a reference. And throughout the story, this reference must be pointed back again and again using words [they] and [them]. The initial reference is called as *Antecedent*, and the next link-backing references are called as *Anaphoric reference*. There is also different pattern of sentence when the anaphoric reference comes first, and the initial reference comes later. This pattern is technically known as *Cataphora* as in:

Yesterday, I walked through the farm and unpredictably I saw *it* in the fish pool. *A big python snake!* [in this sentence, the anaphoric reference *it* comes first, followed by the initial reference *big python snake*]

The use of zero anaphora can create an expectation that the listener can interpret what speaker intends to identify.

A referential approach in semantics is when language is used to refer to something in the world. For example, if you say “I am in Florida” the speaker (you) is the referent of the word *I* and the referent of the word *Florida* is the state of Florida.

Here you can see that there are two different types of reference: constant and variable reference. In the above example, *I* refers to the person who is speaking. This is the **referent**. If I (Josh) said the sentence, the word *I* would be referring to the human Josh. If you said the sentence (feel free to say it out loud right this moment), then the word *I* would refer to the current reader of this website.

A similar example is the term *president of the United States of America*. If you say this at the time of this writing (2019) the term would refer to Donald Trump. The term *the president of the United States of America* would refer to Barack Obama if the phrase was uttered in 2010. This is variable reference.

The word, *Florida*, however, has constant reference. The word *Florida* will always refer to the state of Florida.

Some words do not have something to point to in the real world; they don't have a referent. For example, the word *unicorn* doesn't have a referent as the word cannot point to something that doesn't exist.

Implicature is an essential component of communication and literature that adds layers of meaning and complexity both spoken and written texts. In communication implicature plays a crucial role in conveying the intended message of the speaker or writer as it is often used to imply information that can not or should not be explicitly stated. This allows speakers and writers to communicate ideas implicitly, allowing for nuanced and flexible social interaction. The importance of implicature in communication and literature lies in its ability to enhance communication and understanding by conveying meaning beyond the surface level of words. (Rakhmatova, M2023)

Baker defines reference based on the relationship between words and reality. The linguist states that “the term reference is traditionally used in semantics for the relationship which holds between a word and what it points to in a real world”. However, such definition is too general for Halliday and Hasan as they distinguish situational reference from text reference. Situational reference is known as „exophora“ or „exophoric reference“, whereas a name for reference within text is that of

„endophora“ or „endophoric reference“ The difference between endophora and exophora lies in the context of situation and the context of the text. Both situational and textual reference retrieves the information necessary for the interpreting of the particular element. On one hand, exophoric reference points to something that is outside that text and usually familiar to the receiver because of the familiarity of certain situation. To quote Halliday “exophoric reference means that the identity presumed by the reference item is recoverable from the environment of the text”. On the other hand, endophoric reference indicates something strictly from the text, or as the linguist states, it “means that the identity presumed by the reference item is recoverable from within the text itself - <...> from the instancial system of meanings created as the text unfolds” (Ibid.). Endophoric reference can vary in kind, i.e. it can be anaphoric or cataphoric. Baker points out that “after the initial introduction of some entity, speakers will use various expressions to maintain references”. The key word here is „after“ as anaphora defines a situation in text when the sender refers to something that has already been introduced.

Cohesion - one element in the text is dependent on another for its interpretation - a cohesive link is present between the presupposing & the presupposed items. There are three types of grammatical links or cohesive devices: Reference, substitution and ellipsis, conjunction Ex. “Please don’t do that while I’m trying to work”, she begged. (True to his nature, James started whistling to himself as soon as she settled down to her work. “Please don’t do that while I’m trying to work”, she begged. The reference refers to the dependent relationship between the referring and the referred in a text. There are following types of reference: Exophoric reference (outside) Endophoric reference (inside) Anaphoric (backward) Cataphoric (forward) Reference - personal pronouns (he, she, it, they, etc.), definite article (the), deictics (this/that, these/those, here/there, etc.), same, different, other, else, such. Anaphoric reference looks back in the text. Exophoric reference refers to the world outside the text (not truly cohesive, because it is not text-internal, but part of the reader’s active role in creating coherence). Cataphoric reference: we have to read on to understand the relation between the items and the referents (engaging the reader’s attention) Problems with „it“ and „this“ „that“ Also in other languages we may have problems with some cohesive items („sua“ in Italian her?, you?, she?) One of the main types of reference is cataphora. In linguistics, cataphora was taken from Greek origin, *καταφορά* from *κατά* "forward" and *φέρειν* "carry" is used to describe an expression that co-refers with a later expression in the discourse. That is to say, the earlier expression refers to or describes a forward expression. For example, given: "Finding the right gadget was a real hassle. I finally settled with a digital camera." The "right gadget" is an instance of cataphora because it

refers to "a digital camera," an object that hasn't been mentioned in the discourse prior to that point. Cataphora is a type of endophora and it is the opposite of anaphora, a reference forward as opposed to backward in the discourse. As a general rule, cataphoras are quite less common than anaphoras in all natural languages; furthermore, cataphoras that are not sentence-internal are typically very uncommon in informal, conversational contexts. Cataphora is often used for rhetorical effect. It can build suspense and provide a description. For example: "He's the biggest slob I know. He's really stupid. He's so cruel. He's my boyfriend Nick." Cataphora is sometimes used in subordinate clauses within a sentence. For example: "After he had received his orders, the soldier left the barracks." Cataphora is often used to provide a description in advance of a name. For examples: "If you want them, there are cookies in the kitchen." Reference exophora (situationa l) endophora (textual) anaphora (to preceding text) cataphora (to following text) In linguistics, anaphora (pronounced /ə' næfərə/) is an instance of an expression referring to another. In general, an anaphoric expression is represented by a pro-form or some kind of deictic. In some theories, the strict definition of anaphora includes only references to preceding utterances. A preceding utterance can be anything, such as a noun (see examples below). Under this definition, forward references (where the cataphoric expression refers to a succeeding utterance) are instead named cataphora, and both effects together are endophora. Also, the term exophora names situations where the referent does not appear in the utterances of the speaker, but instead in the real world. Some linguists prefer to define anaphora generically to include all of these referential effects. An exophoric reference refers to language outside of the text in which the reference is found. Some examples in Uzbek: Lekin men o'yinni to'xtatmadim, to'xtatish hotiramga ham kelmagan edi. A homophoric reference is a generic phrase that obtains a specific meaning through knowledge of its context. For example, the meaning of the phrase "the Queen" may be determined by the country in which it is spoken. An endophoric reference refers to something inside of the text in which the reference is found. For example: "You never know a moment's freedom from anxiety and care, never gain a moment's rest for dreamy laziness — no time to watch the window shadows ..." In conclusion, we try to analyze the reference and its main types. In addition, we find out some solutions for translation problems of it.

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